

The Personality of the Main Character in Tiana Amelia's Short Story *Menantu Atau Pembantu: Sigmund Freud's Psychoanalysis Study*

¹Mhd. Azhar Nasution, ²Mutia Nasution²

¹Universitas Sumatera Utara, ²Politeknik Negeri Sriwijaya

Email address: azharnasution44@gmail.com, mutianasution@polsri.ac.id

Received: Nov 11, 2024 | Reviewed: Dec 1, 2024 | Revised: Dec 24, 2024 | Accepted: Dec 26, 2024

ABSTRACT: Research with the title “The personality of the main character in the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia: Sigmund Freud's Psychoanalysis Study”. This study aims to describe the personality of the main character in the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia with story facts as the basis for analysing id, ego, superego in Sigmund Freud's psychoanalysis. The theory used in solving this research problem uses Robert Stanton's story fact theory and Sigmund Freud's personality theory. This type of research uses library research with a descriptive qualitative approach. The data in the research is text in the form of sentence quotations sourced from the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia. The data collection technique uses the reading and note-taking method. The data analysis technique uses the hermeneutic method with analysis steps through data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions. The results of this study show that through the facts of the story in the short story, there is a forward plot that describes the personality of the main character with other characters who support the course of the story. The personality of the character described is also motivated by time, place, and socio-cultural background. The results of the analysis of the personality structure according to Sigmund Freud on the main character named Jesi describe the form of id or Jesi's desire is very large, including the desire to have a mother-in-law who is kind and affectionate to her and does not live in one house with her mother-in-law, but the whole id is not all realised by the ego because it can be controlled by the superego. Among the three personality structures, the superego aspect dominates Jesi. Superego is able to postpone the fulfilment of all aspects of id with reality into the achievement of id fulfilment in morality.

Keywords: *short story Menantu atau Pembantu, the personality of the main character, Sigmund Freud's psychoanalysis Blythe*

INTRODUCTION

Short stories have a lighter storytelling pattern than novels. The definition of short story is stated by Sumardjo and Saini in their book *Apresiasi Kesusastraan*. They understand that a short story (or abbreviated as short story) is a short story. But by only looking at its short physicality one cannot yet determine that a short story is a short story (1986: 36).

Furthermore, according to Priyatni (2010: 126) short stories are a form of fiction. Short stories, as the name implies, show the short nature of the events expressed, the content of the story, the number of actors, and the number of words used. This comparison can be made with

other forms of prose, such as novels.

Apart from being seen as a social phenomenon, literature is also seen as a psychological phenomenon, which displays psychological aspects through characters if the text happens to be in the form of prose or drama. Meanwhile, if the text is in the form of poetry, it will certainly be displayed through typical lines and word choices. Besides, there are lyric poems or ballads that contain certain characters (Endraswara 2004: 96-97).

Human life depicted through characters in literary works is depicted in the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia. Tiana Amelia is a writer from Medan, North Sumatra. Some of Tiana Amelia's short stories were published in Medan newspapers, including the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* published in *Harian Waspada* on 9 February 2022. Through Sigmund Freud's psychoanalysis, the study of this short story focuses on the personality elements of the main character named Jesi.

There are several interesting and important reasons why this research was conducted. The description of the main character named Jesi, a wife who lives with her mother-in-law who is unkind to her daughter-in-law Jesi. This is interesting because in this modern era where women are free to express their opinions. Why does Jesi have the patience to stay with her mother-in-law?

The next interesting thing is the description of several characters in the short story that makes readers furious with these characters, namely the character Adel who is Adel's sister-in-law who lives with them, Jesi's mother-in-law who is cruel to Jesi and Jesi's husband Erlan who is the only character who sides with Jesi.

Furthermore, through Sigmund Freud's psychoanalysis, this research is focused on the personality

problems of the main character named Jesi who has elements of complex personality.

Therefore, based on some background of this problem, the title of this research is “The Personality of the Main Character in the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia: Sigmund Freud’s Psychoanalysis Study”.

Based on the description of the background, the formulation of the problem in this study, how is the personality of the main character in the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia with story facts as a basis for analysing id, ego, superego in Sigmund Freud’s psychoanalysis? The purpose of the research is to describe the main character’s personality in the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia with story facts as the basis for analysing id, ego, superego in Sigmund Freud’s psychoanalysis.

The theoretical benefits of this research will be an additional reference in the development of personality psychology studies in literary works, especially Sigmund Freud’s psychoanalysis, so that readers do not only consider literary works as a means of entertainment but as science and a representation of real life. The practical benefits add to the understanding of all readers regarding the personality of the main character contained in the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* which is represented through literary works. Not only that, it is hoped that the findings of this research analysis can add new scientific works to literary science and the world of education in general.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Story Facts

Stanton (2007: 22) divides the structure into three parts, namely: Story facts, theme, literary means. In this research, only story facts will be used. These elements serve as a record of the imaginative events of a story. When summarised together all these elements are called the ‘factual structure or ‘factual level’ of the story (Stanton, 2007: 22). The plot in a work of fiction is generally a series of stories formed by stages of events so as to weave a story presented by the

actors in a story. The stages of events that weave a story can be formed in a series of various events (Aminuddin, 2015: 83).

Then, characterisation is often equated with character and characterisation refers to the placement of certain characters with certain characters in a story (Nurgiyantoro, 2015: 247). The main character is the character who is prioritised in the novel. He is the character who is told the most. Both as the perpetrator of events and the subject of events (Nurgiyantoro, 2013: 259).

The setting is the environment that surrounds an event in the story, the universe that interacts with ongoing events. The setting can take the form of a decor such as a cafe in Paris, the mountains in California, a dead-end street in the corner of Dublin, and so on. The setting can also take the form of a specific time (day, month, and year), the weather or a period of history (Stanton, 2007: 35).

Short Story

The term prose or fictional literary work is also commonly referred to as prose story, prose narrative, narrative or plot. The definition of prose is a story carried by certain actors with certain roles, settings and stages and series of stories that depart from the results of the author's imagination so as to weave a certain story. Further works of fiction can be distinguished in various forms, be it romances, novels, novelettes, or short stories (Aminuddin, 2015: 66). On the other hand, according to Priyatni (2010: 126), short stories are a form of fiction. Short stories, as the name implies, show a short nature, both the events expressed, the content of the story, the number of actors, and the number of words used. This comparison is in relation to other forms of prose, such as novels

Literary Psychology

According to (Ratna, 2004: 342), definitively, the purpose of literary psychology is to understand the psychological aspects contained in a literary work. However, this does not mean

that the psychological analysis of literature is completely detached from the needs of society. Furthermore, Sehandi (2016: 46) literary psychology is more concerned with characters and characterisation, with three areas of analysis, namely the psychology of authors, the psychology of characters in literary works, and the psychology of literary readers. as a science related to humans (humanities), literary works give considerable intensity to the nature of psychology while utilising it in understanding various problems of human life.

Endraswara (2004: 96), literary psychology is a study of literature that views works as psychological activities. The author will use creation, taste, and work in creating. Likewise, readers, in responding to works, will also not be separated from their respective psyches. The first goal of personality psychology is to obtain information about human behaviour (Minderop, 2011: 8)

Personality According to Sigmund Freud

The personality theory used in this study is Sigmund Freud's personality. In Freud's psychoanalytic theory of personality, personality is seen as a structure consisting of three elements or

systems, namely id, ego, and superego. These three systems are a unified and harmonious arrangement. The following is a description of each of the personality systems formulated by Sigmund Freud:

The id is the most basic personality system, the system in which there are innate instincts, for the other two systems, the id is a system that acts as a provider or distributor of energy needed by these systems for the operation of the activities they carry out. In this matter of energy, the id cannot tolerate the accumulation of energy that can cause a high level of stress on the organism or individual as a whole (Koswara, 1991: 32). In addition, to a certain extent, the libido instinct

makes a very important contribution to the preservation and continuity of human life, because without the libidinal instinct human sustainability would never be maintained (Febriani, 2017: 32). The ego is the force that rejects and suppresses the unconscious, when it comes to the unconscious, how then can we expect justice to be served? The claim of rejecting sexuality stands foremost in this line of suppression, it is natural that from the ego's point of view we can never learn its extent and significance based on reality (Freud, 2020: 395). Furthermore, if this ego performs its implementation actions wisely, there will be harmony and harmony. If the ego defeats or surrenders too much of its power to ideas, to the super ego, or to the external world, there will be confusion and disorder (Hall, 2017: 36-37).

The third important agency of the personality is the superego. The superego is the moral or justice branch of the personality. The superego represents the ideal realm rather than the realm of reality, and it aims towards perfection rather than towards reality or pleasure. The superego develops from the ego as a result of the fusion that a child experiences and the measures of his parents, regarding what is good and wrong, what is bad and hurtful (Hall, 2017: 42).

METHOD

This type of research uses library research with a descriptive qualitative approach. Qualitative research is research used to research on natural object conditions, which makes the researcher a key instrument and the results of qualitative research emphasize meaning rather than generalisation (Sugiyono, 2017: 9).

The data in the research is text in the form of sentence quotations or paragraphs of short stories *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia. Meanwhile, the data source in this research is the book of short stories *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia. The data collection techniques used in this study were reading and note-taking techniques. Data analysis techniques

use data reduction and data presentation.

FINDINGS

This study of personality aspects in the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia only emphasises the main character, Jesi. The personality theory used to analyse Jesi's character uses Sigmund Freud's personality theory which consists of id, ego, and superego. The three personality structures are within humans and cannot be separated. The results of the analysis of the personality structure according to Sigmund Freud on Jesi's character show that Jesi's id or desire is very big to fight her mother-in-law's treatment and get out of the house, but the whole id is not all realised by the ego because it can be controlled by the superego. Among the three personality structures, the superego aspect dominates Jesi. Superego is able to postpone the fulfilment of all aspects of id with reality into the achievement of id fulfilment in morality, for more clarity is described in the table below.

Table 1. Components in *Menantu Atau Pembantu*

Component	Description in <i>Menantu Atau Pembantu</i>	Dominance
Id	Desires to fight her mother-in-law, leave the house	High
Ego	Mediates between the desire to rebel and the need to endure	Moderate
Superego	Emphasizes patience, survival, and moral considerations	High

Id: Represents Jesi's primal urges and desires. It drives her to act impulsively, such as confronting her mother-in-law or leaving the house.

Superego: Acts as her internal moral compass. It promotes patience, encourages her to endure the difficult situation, and emphasizes the importance of morality and societal expectations.

Ego: Mediates between the impulsive desires of the Id and the moral constraints of the Superego. It helps Jesi find a balance between her immediate needs and the long-term

consequences of her actions.

Dominance:

The Superego appears to be the dominant force in Jesi's personality. While the Id is strong, the Superego effectively controls these impulses, leading Jesi to prioritize patience and survival over immediate gratification.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

This study makes a significant contribution to the field of Psychoanalytic literary analysis by extending the application of Sigmund Freud's groundbreaking theories to a contemporary Indonesian short story, *Menantu Atau Pembantu*. By meticulously examining the main character's actions, thoughts, and emotions through the lens of Freud's id, ego, and superego, the study provides valuable insights into the character's underlying motivations, conflicts, and unconscious desires. This in-depth analysis not only enriches the understanding of the short story itself but also demonstrates the enduring relevance and versatility of Psychoanalytic theory in interpreting literary works beyond the traditional scope of Western classics.

Furthermore, this study pioneers the application of Psychoanalytic literary analysis to modern Indonesian literature. By exploring the psychological complexities of a character within this specific cultural context, the research contributes to a deeper understanding of how cultural and societal factors intersect with individual psychology as depicted in literary works. This interdisciplinary approach expands the boundaries of Psychoanalytic literary analysis, encouraging further exploration of the theory's applicability to diverse literary traditions and cultural contexts worldwide.

The results of the analysis of the facts of the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia and the personality of the main character based on Sigmund Freud's personality above, can be explained that the analysis of literary works cannot be separated from its forming structure,

namely intrinsic elements, in Stanton's term called factual structure, although the analysis is focused on the personality of the main character, it does not mean eliminating the forming elements of literary works. The following is a discussion of the facts of the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu*.

The plot used in *Menantu Atau Pembantu* is a forward or progressive plot because the events told in the novel are sequential, starting from the adjustment stage, a stage that contains the description and introduction of the main character, Jesi, a daughter-in-law who is kind, gentle, patient but gets bad treatment from her in-laws.

The conflict emergence stage, at this stage there is a conflict that occurs, namely Jesi getting bad treatment from her mother-in-law such as being treated like a maid and often getting angry.

At the climax stage, the conflict of the story reaches a breaking point. The peak of Jesi's conflict with her mother-in-law occurs during her mother-in-law's birthday. All of Jesi's hard work preparing a birthday surprise was not appreciated by her mother-in-law.

Finally, the resolution stage, the conflict that occurred between Jesi and her mother-in-law began to find common ground when Jesi's husband witnessed his wife being treated badly by her mother until finally Jesi's husband took Jesi's side and invited her to leave the house.

The characters contained in the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia based on their role and importance are divided into two, namely the main character and additional characters. The main character, named Jesi, is kind, gentle and patient. Additional characters include Jesi's cruel mother-in-law, Jesi's kind husband and Jesi's evil and lazy sister-in-law.

The dominant place setting in Additional characters is at home. The time setting mentions morning and afternoon, while the socio-cultural setting in the short story found is the attitude and perspective of an in-law who thinks that a son-in-law must do all the housework in his in-laws' house.

After discussing the facts of the short story, then continued with a discussion of the personality of the main character named Jesi, the personality theory used is personality according to Sigmund Freud. The application of Sigmund Freud's psychology in literature is a way of understanding the psychological aspects of characters through the texts described in literature. Psychology and literature have similar studies, both of which discuss human problems as individual and social beings. The humans studied in psychology are in the real world while literature is in works of fiction.

Jesi experiences psychological turmoil because her desires or wishes are not all realised in reality. This can be seen when her strong desire to fight the mistreatment and get out of her in-laws' house, but superego delays it with actions that are in accordance with morality so that Jesi is forced to be patient and stay in the house.

The superego then controls Jesi's desires. This is in line with what Koswara (1991: 35) explains, that the superego aspect is a personality system that contains values and rules that are related to good and bad. The superego is formed through the internalisation of values or rules by individuals from a number of figures who play a role, are influential or meaningful to the individual such as parents and teachers. The main function of the superego is to control the urges or impulses of the id instinct so that these impulses are channelled in a way or form that is acceptable to society. Jesi's husband realises the suffering his wife is going through and decides to take her out of her mother's house. Jesi's id to get out of the house becomes a reality, this can be seen when Jesi's husband invites Jesi to get out of the house.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The personality structure of Jesi's character in the short story *Menantu Atau Pembantu* by Tiana Amelia has one aspect of id, one aspect of ego, and one superego. Jesi's id to realise her

desires into reality is very big but superego is able to control Jesi's id. There are several conflicts that occur between Jesi's id and superego, but the conflict is controlled by superego. This can be seen when Jesi's id to fight her mother-in-law and get out of the house superego delays the gratification of id. The superego is in the form of advice from within herself to be patient and survive. Among the three personality structures, the superego aspect dominates Jesi. The superego is able to delay the gratification of all aspects of id with reality being the achievement of id gratification in morality.

REFERENCES

- Aminuddin. (2015). *Introduction to the Appreciation of Literary Works*. Bandung: Sinar Baru Algensindo.
- Endraswara, Suwardi. (2004). *Literary Research Methodology: Epistemology, Models, Theories, and Applications*. Yogyakarta: Widyatama Library.
- Freud, Sigmund. (2020). *General Introduction to Psychoanalysis*. Yogyakarta: Indoliteration.
- Febriani, Rika. (2017). *Sigmund Freud vs Carl Jung: A Clash between Schools of Psychoanalysis*. Yogyakarta: Sociality.
- Hall, S. Calvin. (2017). *Sigmund Freud's Power Instinct*. Yogyakarta: Narasi.
- Koswara, E. (1991). *Theories of Personality*. Bandung: Eresco Bandung.
- Minderop, Albertine. (2011). *Literary Psychology*. Jakarta: Yayasan Obor Indonesia.
- Nurgiyantoro, Burhan. (2015). *Theory of Fiction Studies*. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- Ratna, Nyoman Kutha. (2004). *Theories, Methods, and Techniques of Literary Research*. Yogyakarta: Student Library.
- Sehandi, Yohanes. (2016). *Get to know 25 Literary Theories*. Yogyakarta: Ombak.
- Stanton, Robert. (2007). *Robert Stanton's Theory of Fiction (Translation of Sugihastuti and Al Irsyad)*. Yogyakarta: Student Library.
- Sugiyono. (2017). *Qualitative Research Methods*. Bandung: Alfabeta Publisher Bandung.
- Syafuruddin. (2019). *Ratih Without Smartphone*. Yogyakarta: Kalika.
- Wellek, Rene, and Warren. (2014). *Theories of Literature*. Jakarta: Gramedia.